

Species of concern present in reef passages around Ovalau Island

Insights from community interviews in Vatukalo, Tokou and Levuka & underwater video surveys in Toki, Natubari and Nalulu Passages

CR – Critically Endangered, EN – Endangered, VU – Vulnerable, NT – Near Threatened, DD – Data Deficient

CR *Vonu taku*
Hawksbill sea turtle

CR *Qio ulutuki*
Hammerhead shark

EN *Qio [rewa]saqa*
Grey reef shark

EN Whale shark

EN *Tovuto*
Sperm whale

EN *Vai Vuka*
Ocellated eagle ray

EN *Qio saqa*
Bull shark

EN *Varivoce*
Humphead wrasse

VU *Qio dina*
White-tip reef shark

VU *Vai*
Round ribbontail ray

VU *Qio dina*
Black-tip reef shark

VU *Qio dina*
Silvertip shark

DD *Kavu*
Giant grouper

NT *Walu*
Spanish mackerel

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